

Species 1: *H. erato*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.75; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. himera*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.45; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.426

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.034

D
p.value = 0.002

Background 2→1

D
p.value = 0.02632

Background 1→2

D
p.value = 0.0322

Species 1: *H. erato*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.9; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. himera*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.51; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red= $S1 > S2$, Blue= $S1 < S2$, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.358

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.11$

Background 2->1

D

p.value = 0.03333

Background 1->2

D

p.value = 0.01293